

Teachers' professional development on student achievement: perceptions of district superintendents of schools in USA

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ABSTRACT

The perceptions of school superintendents on planning and designing of school teachers' professional development programmes (PDP) place a crucial role in inservice teacher development. The present study aimed to examine the school superintendents' perceptions towards professional development of teachers based on students' academic achievement. The study employed quantitative descriptive research design which included descriptive and inferential statistics to interpret the superintendents' perceptions on teachers' professional development plan. The researchers utilized quantitative surveys to gather data from 128 public school superintendents and captured their perceptions on Teachers PDPs. Findings reported that superintendents' perceived PDPs must integrate knowledge on student achievement, skills needed, and worthwhile-content mastery. Study further revealed that, students' academic achievement details can provide accurate components to be included in teachers PDP. Future researchers may explore the evidence-based planning of PDPs to motivate the teachers' active participation in professional growth activities.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Never before in the history of education had greater importance to the professional development of teachers than now. The proposals for educational reform and plans for school improvement has always emphasized the need for high-quality professional development programme [1]. The ability of a school district to build teachers' professional capacity is a key component of teacher quality and student achievement. Thus, recognizing the significant connection between teachers professional development, teaching quality, and students academic achievement is important to the success of a school superintendents' role. The quality of professional development within a school district can have multiple impacts on the overall operation of a district. More specifically, a growing sentiment is that "teacher educators can only continue to act as professionals if they are engaged in further professional development throughout their career" [2]. Previous studies demonstrated that quality professional development programs positively impacted the teacher retention, staff morale, student achievement, and school climate [3].

The professional development practice principles addressed in this study are based on Timperley and Alton-Lee's [4], 10 principles of professional development highlighted in her work 'teacher professional

learning and development: valued outcomes', which relates specific instructional techniques to student achievement. One of the 10 principles of Timperley and Alton-Lee's [4] is 'worthwhile content' and found to have impact on student achievement. Another principle 'integration of knowledge' implements the instructor's knowledge and skills to incorporate professional growth and positively alter student outcomes. Following which, the principle 'assessment for professional inquiry' relates to what children must be taught and can be done to convey what teachers need to know and teach. The principle 'multiple opportunities to learn and apply information' outlines the importance of educators having various ways to learn and apply the information. The principle 'approaches responsive to learning' address the need for an educator to apply learning and assess if those items learned are consistent with previous knowledge. The seventh principle 'opportunities to process new learning with others' educates the importance of a collegial and collaborative approach to professional development. The principle 'knowledgeable expertise' refers to expert knowledge external to an educator's current system. Furthermore, 'active leadership' is a principle that enforces the idea that leadership matters. Eventually the final principle 'maintaining momentum' emphasizes the need for continuous and long-term growth. Student learning and achievement are the ultimate focus of schools. Marzano [5] identified key components that positively impact student achievement. Marzano [5] presented the quality of classroom curriculum and instruction provided to students has a significant impact on student performance and learning outcomes. Timperley and Alton-Lee's [4] ten principles of professional development are meant to aid educators in developing and implementing professional development plans [4]. They are, i) Valued outcomes: the emphasis placed on student outcomes from a professional learning experience is key and promotes the legitimacy of professional development. ii) Worthwhile content: quality professional development prepares educators to work within a program that consistently supports the building of quality pedagogic approaches. iii) Integration of knowledge and skills: an educator's instructional skills must be sharp, but their fundamental understanding of why those practices or others are effective is equally essential. vi) Assessment for professional inquiry: educators must possess strong assessment skills to fully understand what their students understand and what ways may be working to increase student performance. v) Approaches responsive to learning: educators need to encounter these opportunities in environments that offer both trust and challenge". vi) Multiple opportunities to learn and apply information: educators have many ideas about how students learn, what is worth learning, and their respective roles in achieving this. vii) Opportunities to process new learning with others: collaboration and learning as a social function are fundamental to multiple adult learning theories [4]. The professional climate educators work in must promote positive professional communication. viii) Knowledgeable expertise: supporting the previous principle, this component invites outside expertise into the development program to challenge assumptions, break habits, and cultivate creativity, all while incorporating a field expert to increase validity and reliability. ix) Active leadership: principle nine encourages educators to become leaders in the professional development process and within their respective systems. Without leaders, the change our students need isn't happening". x) Maintaining momentum: moving forward and striving for increased student outcomes must stay moving. The continuous professional development process of inquiry, action, and reflection upholds the natural momentum of professional growth and teacher improvement.

Teachers' professional development is a regular academic activity conducted every year by school superintendents of each district in United States. Traditionally, the source for creating the professional development programmes (PDP) components largely focuses on strengthening the technological, pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK) of teachers. The outcomes of such PDPs did not benefit the teachers optimally. Thus, present study proposes a new PDP framework which emphasizes understanding of school performance indices, school superintendents' years of experience and the size of their school districts (small or large) in providing effective PDP for teachers. The study sets a new trend in conducting teachers PDPs unlike the traditional ideology and provides empirical evidence. The outcome of the study help designing teachers PDPs more meaningfully by district superintendents in the new normal and in the future.

2. THE COMPREHENSIVE THEORETICAL BASIS

2.1. The role of school leaders

Principals face many professional challenges when leading the schools. They could be school-dependent and school-independent [6]. However, the cooperation of parents is necessary for students to carry out their creative activities without any hindrance [7]. Establishing occupational ideals and standards and providing recommendations on necessary knowledge and abilities for greater professional legitimacy and credibility was driving the push for professionalism [8]. One way to conceptualize professional development is as the collaborative component of professional learning or as a synonym for professional learning [8]. With the assistance of superintendent learning managers and outside consultants, negotiations have made it feasible to shift the educational system's bureaucracy from top-down to more peer-led forms of professional

development [8]. States and local school districts may need to implement a mechanism that links the principal assessment process to a high level of student success to guarantee that capable principals are in charge of our country's schools [9].

To ensure students advance, the school leader must foster an environment of excellence while encouraging students to take calculated risks, think creatively, be original thinkers, and take responsibility for their education [10]. Effective school leaders prioritize teaching and learning, have strong interpersonal skills, will be people-oriented, and will have the ability to solve problems and manage people in novel ways [11]. Principal's leadership skills and school development are inextricably linked. Pursuing the relationship between principal's professional development, equity, student improvement, and teacher performance and retention demonstrates the growth and benefits of leadership [12]. Principals are essential in initiating and leading professional discussions that can influence school teaching practices [13]. Meanwhile, means should be put in place to ensure that the principal's professional development is not subject to any challenges [14]. It is necessary to cooperate with the school community principal's activities and support development activities, such as implementing new teaching methods or adopting innovative technologies [15]. There are many traits of successful principals' leadership in professional development, and a few studies emphasize particular behaviours and arrangements that have been demonstrated to support students' development [16]. The school's principal can precisely control the role and structure of professional development in schools. Principals are aware of the pedagogical and subject matter requirements of their instructors as well as the background of their school [17]. Principals are essential in initiating and leading professional discussions that can influence school teaching practices [18].

2.2. Perspectives on professional development programmes at schools

Professional development might be a key strategy for successfully implementing education in school and used to bring about student improvement [19]. The principals emphasized several elements crucial to their professional development and established and contested the meaning of the framework for professional learning in many ways [20]. Farah [21] asserted that the principal is the school's manager and leader; however, to stand the crowd, this position requires training and experience. They placed a high value on networking and interacting with colleagues, as they were perceived to be the most efficient, advantageous, and pertinent form of professional development [22]. The principal of the school ought to handle professional development more intimately. More widely available technology creates new opportunities for students to be involved in learning [23]. While learning and professional development are essential in all areas for schools to succeed, instructional leadership is the most desirable skill for school leaders to acquire throughout their professional development [24]. School teachers influence the school's smooth and efficient functioning and contribute to students' development [25]. The principal's leadership character should be demonstrated to enhance learning and other aspects of the school so that other school principals and educational practitioners can benefit from their respective school environments and educational systems [26]. Effective school leadership often influences the development of student performance. Linked to better school climate and increased teacher and student satisfaction [27]. Dhuey and Smith [28] asserted that strategically placing skilled supervisors can help bridge achievement gaps, but principals' experience only significantly affects student performance. A superintendent's interaction with other neighbourhood schools influences his school's improvement [29]. It is found that, by creating a professional non-competitive environment between schools in the neighbourhood can get productive output to schools [30].

Thus far PDPs mostly focused on school environment, faculty members, education system, teaching-learning processes and so on. Traditional PDPs were mostly based on teachers input or teachers' weaknesses or based on student feedback. There is less effort in understanding PDPs based on students' performance indicators and achievement data. The student-achievement result analysis data can speak louder than the traditional ideas and can create opportunities for developing effective PDPs for teachers. Therefore, in the current study taps the idea of perceiving students' achievement data as one of the main resources to frame teachers PDP by school superintendents. As it is evidence based and has the potential to support school superintendents enhance the quality of school education within their jurisdiction. Therefore, present study measures the effectiveness of teacher PDPs by comparing the traditionally developed PDPs and the newly developed PDPs which are driven by students' performance data.

2.3. Theoretical framework

The district superintendents cover many different missions, including leadership, monitoring, teachers' professional development, student discipline and student achievement, which reflect the effectiveness of the students [31]. For that, it is a very important mission and one of the most important aims of the educational process. From the perspective of district superintendents in the USA. Scholars mainly use relevant theories, such as the theory of change, adaptive leadership theory, and adult learning theory, to successfully establish a theoretical framework and build up the study for evaluating teachers' professional

development and its impacts on student achievement. Therefore, the change theory of reform emphasizes that teachers learn together [32]. Teacher networks and work-embedded learning improve teaching methods, improving student outcomes. Adaptive leadership theory also sheds light on how superintendents overcome barriers to implementing good practices [33], emphasizing the importance of coping with resources and social resistance within districts. The adult learning theory is another important paradigm for comprehending how teachers interact with professional development [34]. Based on this theory, the school superintendent is responsible for promoting adult learning activities that are appropriate for all employees of his organization and guiding students. This theory helps principals to be goal-oriented while creating a way for teachers to use their professional development [35]. Furthermore, integrating multiple educational perspectives underscores the need for a comprehensive strategy for district policies that facilitates effective professional development and makes a clear connection between these policies and student academic achievement [36]. Through an understanding of learning principles, adult learners' characteristics, professional development's transformative potential, school effectiveness, and change processes, this framework provides a holistic lens for examining superintendents' perceptions of the effectiveness of professional development programs in raising student achievement. Thus, the above discussions led to the following problem statement.

2.4. Problem statement

The present study explores the relationship between teachers PDP and school performance indices. Study further explores the impact of teachers' PDPs developed based on earlier principles and the newly implemented principles. In addition, study attempts to understand if school superintendents' years of experience and the size of their school districts (small or large) matters in providing effective PDP.

3. METHOD

The study applied a descriptive survey research design. It investigated the relationship between the new PDP developed based on past student achievement data and student achievement as school performance index (SPI) score after conducting the newly developed PDP. Furthermore, the study also explored the relationship between newly developed PDP principles and the principles of past PDP. The study further explored the differences in professional development practices based on school superintendents' years of experience. The study sample included 128 public school superintendents in America. An email was sent to school superintendents, which included an invitation to participate in the study, an informed consent form, a request to provide contact information for any questions or concerns, and an electronic link to the survey questionnaire. Of the 128 surveys administered, 72 surveys were returned, with a response rate of 56.7%. Participants in the survey were asked to identify their years of superintendent experience and their respective high school enrollment. Forty-five (62.5%) respondents had 0-10 years of superintendent experience, and 27 (37.5%) had 11 or more years of superintendent experience.

3.1. Survey questionnaire validation

The researcher developed the survey questionnaire based on the 10 principles of professional development from the framework of Timperley and Alton-Lee's [4] report on teacher professional learning and development. The survey booklet can be responded to through text entry and rating selection utilizing a 5-point likert-type scale varying from strongly disagree to strongly agree (1-5). The researcher established the content and face validity of the instrument with the help of 3 subject experts in the field. Further, the reliability of the survey questionnaire was established using Cronbach Alpha internal consistency statistics on a small sample. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.863 indicated that the scale was highly reliable. The survey instrument is available on survey monkey, a web-based data collection platform. Furthermore, the University of South Dakota Institutional Review Board (IRB) approved the survey instrument.

3.2. Data collection

Researchers collected the data through an online survey platform called SurveyMonkey. All eligible participants were administered the survey through a cover letter and a web link on email. The survey link was hyperlinked to the survey page on the website and when clicked, directed the participants to the survey instrument page. Further a follow-up email was sent after a week's time to those who have not completed the survey and were encouraged to complete the same. Student achievement (SPI) and enrollment data were collected from the Midwest State's Department of Education public report card website. Using a quantitative methodology and descriptive statistics, the study examined survey information from 128 superintendents of public schools. Researchers conducted a normality test to decide if the research data should be processed through parametric or non-parametric analysis. The relationships were tested using the correlation test, mean

differences among demographic variables were tested via *t*-tests and eventually, percentage analysis gave an account of the descriptive statistics of the data.

3.3. Ethical considerations

The IRB at the university has approved the study. Furthermore, the survey questionnaire had informed consent at the beginning to be signed. The participants also had the privilege of withdrawing themselves from the survey at any point in time if they were not comfortable answering the survey questions. Additionally, the researchers assured each participant that their collected data would be kept confidential and utilized exclusively for the present study and publication only.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researchers found that the data collected were normal based on the shapiro-wilk normality test ($p > 0.05$). Thus, as planned, researchers conducted pearson correlation coefficient statistical tests and independent sample *t*-tests. Researchers investigated the relationship between the new PDP developed based on past student achievement data and student achievement as SPI score after conducting the newly developed PDP. Researchers employed a correlation test (pearson), the results of which are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Showing the result of the correlation test between new PDP and Student achievement scores

Sl. no	Pearson correlation between	N	Sig.	r-value
1	New PDP (developed based on past student achievement data) * student achievement scores (SPI score after conducting the newly developed PDP)	127	.000	.782
2	Newly developed PDP principles overall scores * the principles of past PDP overall scores	127	.000	.812

From Table 1, serial number 1, it is noted that there exists a high positive correlation ($r=0.782$, $p < 0.05$) between new PDP (developed based on past student achievement data) and student achievement scores (SPI score after conducting the newly developed PDP). Table 1, serial number 2, shows a high positive correlation ($r=0.812$, $p < 0.05$) between newly developed PDP principles and the principles of past PDP. Further, the correlation tests for the ten principles in the newly developed PDP and student achievement scores are computed and interpreted based on Cohen's suggestion that the *r*-value greater than ± 0.5 is considered large. Findings revealed that six of the ten correlation test results are large in the current study. The largest correlations are associated with the principles of *active leadership* ($r=0.657$), *worthwhile content* ($r=0.653$), and *assessment for professional inquiry* ($r=0.627$). The weakest, albeit moderate, correlation is the *integration of knowledge and skills* ($r=0.429$). The researchers explored if school superintendents differed in their perception of the 10 principles of newly developed professional development (developed based on the outline of Timperley and Alton-Lee's [4] report) based on their years of experience as school superintendents. The superintendents' experiences are categorized into: i) superintendents with ten years of experience and ii) superintendents with more than ten years of experience. To test this, researchers employed independent-sample *t*-tests, the results of which are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Showing the results of *t*-tests for each of the ten principles and superintendents' experience

Professional development principles	Superintendent professional experience		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i> value
	10/fewer (mean)	11/more (mean)		
Valued outcomes	3.49	3.48	.032	.974
Worthwhile content	3.87	4.04	-.881	.381
Integration of knowledge and skills	3.71	4.11	-2.029	.046*
Assessment for professional inquiry	3.36	3.19	.708	.481
Multiple opportunities to learn and apply information with others	3.76	3.63	.538	.592
Approaches responsive to learning	3.56	3.52	.162	.872
Opportunities to process new learning with others	3.76	3.67	.422	.674
Knowledgeable expertise	3.62	3.78	-.707	.482
Active leadership	3.73	3.67	.269	.789
Maintaining momentum	3.29	3.26	.127	.899

From Table 2 it is clear that, there existed a significant difference between the superintendents' groups on the principle of '*integration of knowledge and skills*' ($M_{(<ten\ years)}=3.71$, $M_{(>ten\ years)}=4.11$, $t=-2.029$, $p=0.046$). Superintendents with more than ten years of experience had a higher mean value than superintendents with less than ten years of experience. Senior superintendents believe *integrating knowledge and skills* is more important in the Faculty Development Programme (FDP). Researchers further explored if school superintendents differed

in their perception of the 10 principles of newly developed professional development (developed based on the outline of Timperley and Alton-Lee's [4] report) with their job enrollment type. The superintendent's job enrollment type is categorized into: i) superintendents from small school districts and ii) superintendents from large school districts. To test this, researchers employed independent-sample *t*-tests, the results of which are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Showing *t*-test results for ten PDP principles and superintendents from large/small school districts

Professional development principles	Superintendents from		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i> value
	Large school district (mean)	Small school district (mean)		
Valued outcomes	3.41	3.39	.032	.974
Worthwhile content	3.78	4.01	-.881	.381
Integration of knowledge and skills	3.69	4.08	-.029	.346
Assessment for professional inquiry	3.35	3.20	.708	.481
Multiple opportunities to learn and apply information with others	3.73	3.62	.538	.592
Approaches responsive to learning	3.59	3.49	.162	.872
Opportunities to process new learning with others	3.81	3.71	.422	.674
Knowledgeable expertise	3.97	3.37	-2.985	.004*
Active leadership	3.95	3.46	-2.094	.040*
Maintaining momentum	3.28	3.25	.127	.899

*Significant at 0.05 level

From Table 3, the *t*-test results compare the mean difference between each implemented professional development principle and the enrollment in district's high school, indicating two differences that are significant. Superintendents from larger school districts ($M=3.97$) considered the *knowledgeable expertise* principle to be implemented in their districts to a greater extent than those in smaller districts ($M=3.37$, $t=-2.985$, $p=0.004$). Similarly, superintendents from larger school districts ($M=3.95$) considered the Active leadership principle to be implemented in their districts to a greater extent than those in smaller districts ($M=3.46$, $t=-2.094$, $p=0.040$). No other comparisons by district type were significant.

Lastly, the survey's final question asked participants which of the ten principles they perceived as most and least implemented and which should ideally be implemented and not be implemented. The data revealed that the principles perceived to be implemented to the greatest extent are *worthwhile content* and *integration of knowledge and skills*. The principles perceived to be implemented to the least extent are *Maintaining momentum* and *assessment for professional inquiry*. Furthermore, the principles that are perceived as being ideally implemented to the greatest extent are *multiple opportunities to learn and apply information* and *worthwhile content*. The principle perceived to be ideal not to implement is *maintaining momentum*, as revealed by the participants.

Overall, results showed that superintendents firmly believe that 'worthwhile content and 'integration of knowledge and skills' are essential for successful professional growth. These components, meanwhile, were also found to be the least successfully used. These results indicate a sizable discrepancy between the actual use of crucial elements of professional growth and their perceived relevance.

- Discussion and recommendations for practice

The present study found what it intended to find. A significant positive correlation was observed between the SPI and teachers PDPs. Furthermore, the study revealed a positive correlation between earlier PDP and the newly developed PDP. Professional development is a key component of school improvement plans mandated by the state per federal guidelines. Excellent professional development does not guarantee student achievement, but it is critical in the development of instructors. The lack of relationship between professional development principles and student achievement does not indicate that professional development is unimportant or ineffective but rather supported at a greater level in struggling schools. The following practice recommendations emerged from the findings and conclusions of the study. All superintendents must realize the importance of providing quality professional development opportunities. Such realization can occur through quality graduate-level leadership programs that prepare superintendents and accountability measures from the Midwest State's Department of Education. Professional development should be based on principles such as Timperley and Alton-Lee's [4] principles. Superintendents should continue to lead the implementation of the principles they believe should be implemented.

Senior or more experienced school superintendents felt that integrating required knowledge and skill training in PDPs enhances their productivity rather than conducting PDPs for their own sake. Thus, the study expanded on the previous work of Novick [37], identifying time as a major barrier to the implementation of professional development. Novick [37] revealed that working to find time or make time for professional

development is an obstacle that educational leaders responsible for implementing professional development must work innovatively to overcome. Superintendents enrolled in large school districts believed that i) *knowledgeable expertise* and ii) *active leadership* are the key to effective and successful PDP for teachers, as the current study tested the PDP outline of Timperley and Alton-Lee's [4] report. Educating and training administrators primarily takes place at the graduate level within universities. Graduate programs in education must educate future school administrators on the best practices for providing professional development to teachers guided by professional development principles. Leadership is about building and maximizing an organisation's human capital and identifying the needs of teachers; professional development must be teacher-driven and responsive to the needs of a school. Educational leaders responsible for designing and implementing professional development must ground their professional development programs in theory and best practices. Professional learning communities provide a platform for professional development guided by the ten principles of professional development utilized within this study. Providing a group of instructors the opportunity to engage in collaborative work that focuses on instruction and curriculum is a powerful tool when working to lead professional capacity building.

Out of the ten principles of PDP outlined in Timperley and Alton-Lee's [4] report, school superintendents of the USA perceived that *worthwhile content* and *integration of knowledge and skills* required of teachers are the most important principles to be taken care of in teachers' FDP across the United States of America. Mitchell [38] also observed that worthwhile content and integrating knowledge and skills in professional development are key to professional development. They further revealed that the principle of maintaining momentum and assessment for professional inquiry should be considered less, according to their opinion. However, in ideal conditions, they perceived that the principles: i) *multiple opportunities to learn and apply information* and ii) *worthwhile content* to be implemented. Kuhn *et al.* [35] emphasise the importance of collaboration, and the ability to process learning in multiple ways are the key aspects of PDPs. Kuhn *et al.* [35] found that increasing collaboration among staff results in sharing strategies and ideas that may improve instruction and curriculum within an educational system.

Eventually, the superintendents perceived that the principle of maintaining momentum may not be required in ideal conditions [39]. A superintendent must practice and provide active leadership in professional development to his or her respective district [40]. Superintendents should use multiple strategies to provide adequate time to staff for professional development [36]. Superintendents should develop a state-wide or regional professional development network to promote collaboration and small school content-specific teachers' ability to collaborate professionally on instruction and curriculum [41].

5. CONCLUSION

The present study emphasised that the school superintendents affect the teachers' professional development and the student's learning development. That is, it reveals many possible contradictions from the perspective of district superintendents; the research reveals that integration of knowledge and skills and worthwhile content are deemed vital components of effective professional development for teachers. Although superintendents promote teachers' professional development, budgetary constraints and political and social pressures may influence their decisions more than actual field evidence. This situation is more likely an opportunity for professional development issues than others.

Irrespective of the practices of district superintendents in the United States towards conducting teachers' FDPs, this research highlights the critical role of teacher professional development in improving student achievement. These findings underscore the importance of targeted professional development opportunities for educators aligned with district goals and student needs and established recommendations. Systematic programs to improve the professional quality of teachers and student outcomes have been developed through the activities of superintendents. Investing in effective professional development is critical to fostering academic excellence and addressing the diverse needs of students. This study offers insightful information about how superintendents might improve professional development initiatives and give a clearer understanding of what is required to promote educational leadership in the United States.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

All authors have agreed to the content presented in the manuscript.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data of the study is available with one of the authors and may be requested through corresponding author.

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